

**EXTRACTION OF NANOCELLULOSE FROM SECONDARY WASTES
OF THE PAPER INDUSTRY**

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Abstract: Nanocellulose was obtained on the basis of secondary raw materials of the paper industry. The properties of the obtained nanocellulose were studied. The fields of application of nanocellulose are analyzed.

Keywords: Nanocellulose, paper, cellulose, polymer, annual plant, polyacrylic acid, polymethyl vinylpyridine

Cellulose is mainly found in some plant seed feather, seed feather (97-98%), wood (40-50%, dry matter count), hemp stem fiber, the inner layer of plant bark (80-90% in flax), annual plant stems (cane, corn, bushy plant, sunflower), 30-40% in potato knot, 20% in potato knot. Pure cellulose is a tasteless, fibrous white substance. Cellulose is extracted from natural materials by exposing non-cellulose components to decomposing or solvent reagents. The way to distinguish cellulose depends on the composition and structure of the plant material. A gentle method is used to obtain cellulose from cotton fibers. Cotton wool is boiled for 3-6 hours at a pressure of 3-10 atmospheres with a 1.5—3% solution of corrosive sodium (NaOH) and bleached with oxidizers. Mol. m. small polysaccharides (pentozanes, hexosanes, uronic acid), oil and wax pass into the solution.

Cellulose is a white fibrous material, with a density of 1.52—1.54 g/cm³ (at 20°). By its chemical nature, cellulose is a polyatomic alcohol. Since the macromolecule is

a hydroxyl group in the elementary zvenose, cellulose reacts with alkaline metals and bases. In addition to chemical reactions, physico-chemical processes occur when the cellulose is exposed to a concentrated alkali solution, that is, the cellulose decays. From the reaction of cellulose with a concentrated NaOH solution, artificial fibers and simple cellulose esters are used in the textile industry. The practical importance of the synthesis of stitched sopolimers is important in obtaining cellulose materials with new valuable technical properties. Cellulose sopolimers sewn with polyelectrolytes (polyacrylic acid, polymethyl vinylpyridine) can be used as ion-exchange tissues, fibers, and films. Since the simple zvenos of the cellulose macromolecule have a hydroxyl group, simple and complex ethers can be obtained from them. Since these compounds have valuable properties, they are used as fibers, films, lacquer and electrical insulation coatings in various technical areas, suspension stalibizers and thickeners in the oil and textile industry.

Nanocellulose obtained by acid hydrolysis with high precision and purified waste paper (5g) were mixed by adding 60 wt% H_2SO_4 at $45^{\circ}C$. The optimal reaction time was set at 1 h and the fiber-to-liquid ratio was maintained at 1:20. Deionized water was then added to the mixture to terminate the reaction of H_2SO_4 with the paper pulp. The mass was centrifuged to remove H_2SO_4 from the mixture. Next, the nanocellulose is filtered and washed several times with distilled water, placed in a dialysis bag with a molecular weight of 12,000-14,000, and dialyzed until reaching a neutral medium. The resulting nanocellulose was molded for 20 minutes and stored in a refrigerator at $4^{\circ}C$. As the main raw material, cellulose of the flax plant crushed to the level of 46.2 ShR was used. The concentration of the prepared mass is 1%. Then, different compositions of nanocellulose were added to the mass during the mixing process. After that, the mixture of pulp and nanocellulose was sent to the mesh table and the paper was dried under vacuum at $105^{\circ}C$ for 15 minutes. The resulting paper was then placed in a controlled temperature and humidity chamber with a constant temperature of $25^{\circ}C$ and 60% relative humidity to equilibrate the moisture before mechanical testing. For comparison, different percentages of CMCs (5–10%) were added to the mass in the

same way as nanocellulose during the mixing process. Then, after the above process with the addition of nanocellulose, paper reinforced with CMCs was obtained.

Figure 1. The effect of the amount of nanocellulose and CMC on the indices of elongation, explosion and tear of paper sheets.

Effect of nanocellulose on physical properties of paper. With an abundance of surface hydroxyl groups, large specific surface area, high aspect ratio, excellent mechanical properties, and high heat resistance, nanocellulose has demonstrated its potential as a reinforcement in papermaking and to increase the strength of paper sheets. Nanocellulose and CMCs have been used in papermaking to improve the physical performance of paper sheets without structural damage to the fibers. In the current study, flax plant cellulose nanocellulose and CMCs were added to the pulp for papermaking. In addition, the effects of additives with different dimensions were evaluated on the tensile strength, tear index, burst index and elongation of the paper sheets with the results shown in Figure 1. The tensile strength of the paper sheets was increased by the addition of nanocellulose, which caused the creation of bonds between

the fibers. More specifically, the tensile index was increased to a maximum value at the level of 5.5-6% nanocellulose, which was 32.75% higher than that of non-nanocellulose paper sheets.

The maximum values of burst index, tear index and elongation of paper sheets were obtained at 5.5-6 wt% nanocellulose content. These measures were increased by 41.45%, 11.01% and 12.25% respectively. In this study, the effect of CMCs as an additive in papermaking was also measured. Figure 1 shows a comparison of the effects of different amounts of additives on physical properties. With the addition of 5.5-6% nanocellulose and 5.5-6% CMCs, the tensile index reached the maximum values of 40.55% and 37.55%, respectively.

Conclusion. The best ink removal conditions for waste paper were determined as follows: TEM showed nanocellulose to be 300 nm to 600 nm in length and 10 nm to 30 nm in width. Nanocellulose improved the physical properties of paper sheets. These physical properties reached maximum values with the addition of 5.56% nanocellulose.

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